

A Comparison of Erector Spinae Block and Pectoralis Nerve Block in Breast Cancer Patients Undergoing Modified Radical Mastectomy: A Randomized Controlled Trial

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Abstract:

Background: Around 60% of patients have moderate to severe pain after mastectomy in the immediate post-operative period and 20-50% of patients develop chronic post mastectomy pain. This randomised controlled double blinded study was conducted to compare the pectoral nerves block (PECS) and the Erector Spinae Plane block (ESPB) for post-operative analgesia in patients undergoing modified radical mastectomy.

Methods: 60 ASA grade I-II female patients of 18–65 years, undergoing modified radical mastectomy under general anaesthesia were divided into two groups. Group ESPB patients received ultrasound guided erector spinae plane block and Group PECS patients received ultrasound guided PECS block on the affected side after induction of general anaesthesia. The 0-10 scaled Visual analogue scales (VAS) was recorded at 0, 2, 4, 6, 8 and 24 hours post-operative period. The time to first rescue analgesia, number of patients requiring rescue analgesic, complications of block, adverse events and patients' satisfaction score by Quality of Recovery (QoR) survey were recorded.

Results: There was no statistically significant difference in VAS scores between the two groups. However, number of rescue analgesics needed was less in PECS group and the median time to first rescue analgesia was longer for PECS than ESPB group [P<0.001].

Conclusion: Both PECS and ESPB are effective in modified radical mastectomy as there is no difference found between both groups.

Keywords: Mastectomy, modified radical; Postoperative pain; Nerve blocks; Ultrasound imaging.

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Introduction

Modified radical mastectomy (MRM) is a procedure done in which the entire breast is removed, including the skin, areola, nipple and most axillary lymph nodes sparing the pectoralis major muscle. Around 60% of patients complain of moderate to severe pain in the immediate post-operative period [1]. In addition, chronic post mastectomy pain is present in 20-50% of patients and the pain can persist up to two to three years after surgery [2]. Modified radical mastectomy is usually performed under general anaesthesia (GA) along with multimodal analgesia that includes the use of intravenous pharmacological analgesics (opioids, NSAIDs) and pain relief blocks such as the conventional thoracic epidural and paravertebral blocks.

Paravertebral block is an invasive block that requires advanced skill and has increased risks of

complications such as pneumothorax, neuraxial spread, and systemic toxicity due to damage to the nearby pleura and intercostal neurovascular bundles. The thoracic epidural too has risks of neuraxial injuries, epidural hematoma, hypotension and sensory motor block that may affect the quality of recovery. With the use of the ultrasound, fascial plane blocks such as the pectoral nerves block and the erector spinae plane block are being performed with much ease and safety and have reduced the use of opioids, providing excellent analgesia in the intra and post-operative period [3].

The advantages of using ultrasound guided fascial plane blocks are precision, ease of performance and avoidance of complications like pneumothorax and vascular injuries. It avoids sympathetic block and thus hypotension seldom occurs and the patients can be mobilised quickly in the immediate post-

operative period. The PECS fascial block has been found to be a simple, superficial and safe procedure to anaesthetize the hemithorax with a definite analgesic effect in modified radical mastectomy [4]. It involves depositing local anaesthetics between the pectoralis major and pectoralis minor muscles (PECS I) and pectoralis minor and serratus anterior muscles (PECS II), at the levels of the third and fourth ribs, along the mid-axillary line. It blocks the T2–T6 intercostal nerves, medial and lateral pectoral nerves, and intercostobrachial and long thoracic nerves.

Erector Spinae Plane Block (ESPB) is a safe and simple technique and has been successfully used to provide analgesia in thoracic and thoracoabdominal surgeries since 2016. In this technique local anaesthetic is injected into the fascial plane situated between the transverse process of the vertebra and the erector spinae muscles. It blocks the dorsal and ventral rami of the thoracic and abdominal spinal nerves, and the anterior, posterior, and lateral branches of thoracic and abdominal walls. The mechanisms of action and spread of LA are not fully known. Paravertebral spread of local anaesthetics and injection spread from the site to three vertebral levels cranially and four levels caudally were seen. Epidural spread of local anaesthetics has been observed but exact volume and choice of local anaesthetics are not established clearly. In addition to its effect at the rami communicans that supply the sympathetic chain, the erector spinae plane is larger than the epidural space as the erector spinae muscle runs along the length of the thoracolumbar spine, thus providing extensive craniocaudal spread. It has a very low rate of complications consisting of pneumothorax and unintended motor block [5,6].

This prospective randomised controlled double blinded study was conducted to compare PECS block and ESPB for post-operative analgesia in patients undergoing modified radical mastectomy.

Primary objective was to compare the VAS score between the two groups in 24 hours post-operative period. Secondary objectives were to note the time to first rescue analgesia after administration of block, number of patients requiring rescue analgesics, complications of block and patient satisfaction score. Patient satisfaction score was assessed by QoR (Quality of recovery) 15 survey score at preop and post op day 1. Any other adverse events like nausea, vomiting, hypotension, bradycardia, dry mouth, dizziness, and diplopia, complications of the block were recorded.

Methods

After obtaining institutional ethical board clearance, 60 ASA grade I–II female patients in the age group of 18–65 years, undergoing modified radical mastectomy under general anaesthesia were

included in the study. It was a prospective randomised controlled double blinded study conducted at Dr B. Borooah Cancer Institute, Guwahati from January 2021 to December 2021. 60 ASA grade I–II female patients in the age group of 18–65 years undergoing unilateral modified radical mastectomy under general anaesthesia were included. Patients with pre-existing infection at the block site, refusal to give consent, bilateral MRM, coagulopathy, morbid obesity (BMI >40 kg m⁻²), allergic to local anaesthetics, decreased pulmonary reserve, major cardiac disorders, renal dysfunction, pre-existing neurological deficits, and psychiatric illness were excluded.

Patients were randomly allocated into two groups using computer-generated random numbers (Windows Random Allocation Software 2.0). The group allocation numbers were concealed in sealed opaque envelopes by an anaesthetist not involved in the preoperative or postoperative assessment of the patient, anaesthesia management or data collection; and was opened only after shifting the patient to the operation theatre. Patients were also blinded to the study.

Group ESPB patients received ultrasound guided erector spinae plane block and Group PECS patients received ultrasound guided PECS block on the affected side.

In the operating room theatre, after doing the standard machine checks, and keeping emergency drugs and equipment ready, standard ASA monitoring was applied. 18 Gauge IV cannula was secured and the patients were preoxygenated with 100% oxygen for 3 min.

Patients were premedicated with inj palanosetron 0.075 mg iv over ten seconds, inj tramadol 1.5 mg per kg iv diluted to 10 ml slow iv and induced with inj. propofol 2mg per kg iv and inj succinylcholine 1.5 mg per kg iv. Tracheal intubation was done with appropriate size endotracheal tube. Anaesthesia was maintained with inj. vecuronium loading dose of 0.1 mg per kg iv and one fifth of its dose intermittently and nitrous oxide and oxygen in the ratio of 60:40 and isoflurane 0.2% to 1%.

For group ESPB, the patient was put in the lateral position on the side to be blocked. The back was cleaned with full aseptic and antiseptic precautions and a high-frequency Ultrasound linear array transducer probe 6-13MHz was cleaned with chlorhexidine 2% and isopropyl alcohol 70% and covered with a sterile sheet. It was placed longitudinally 3 cm lateral to the T5 spinous process. Three muscles would be seen as follows: trapezius, rhomboid major, and erector spinae. An 8cm 22G nerve locator block needle (Stimuplex®) was then inserted in a cephalocaudal direction until its tip lay in the plane between rhomboid major and erector spinae muscles. The correct placement was

indicated by the linear fluid spread of local anaesthetics that would lift the erector spinae muscle off the underlying transverse processes and intercostal muscles. After confirming the spread with 5 ml of normal saline, 25 ml of 0.25% levobupivacaine was injected. In group PECS, with the same probe and asepsis, pectoral nerve block was performed on the side of surgery with the patient in the supine position and the arm abducted. Infraclavicular region was scanned to locate the axillary artery and vein. The probe was thereafter moved laterally until pectoralis minor and serratus anterior muscles were identified at the level of third rib. 20 ml of 0.25% levobupivacaine was then injected between pectoralis major and minor muscle and 10 ml was injected between pectoralis minor and serratus anterior muscle with 50 mm 24G nerve locator needle. In both the cases local anaesthetic doses did not exceed maximum limit of 3 mg per kg of levobupivacaine. The ECG and SpO₂ were monitored continuously, and heart rate and noninvasive blood pressure were recorded at baseline, after performing the block, and every 5 minutes for 30 minutes.

Inj paracetamol 20 mg per kg IV infusion was given intraoperatively. At the end of the surgery patients were reversed and extubated and shifted to PACU. Postoperative analgesia was provided with intravenous tramadol 1- 1.5 mg kg IV every 8 hourly and inj paracetamol 20 mg per kg IV 8 hourly. Pain was evaluated by the 0 to 10 Visual Analogue Scales (VAS) immediately at the time of arrival in PACU and after 2, 4, 6, 12, and 24 h post op.

Any block-related complications, such as hypotension, vascular puncture, pneumothorax

were looked out for. Rescue analgesia was given with intravenous diclofenac sodium 1-1.5 mg per kg IV bolus, whenever VAS was ≥ 4 . The number of patients requiring rescue analgesia and the time to the first dose of rescue analgesic was recorded. Any other adverse events like nausea, vomiting, hypotension, bradycardia, dry mouth, dizziness, and diplopia, complications of the block were recorded. Patient satisfaction score was assessed by Quality of recovery (QoR) 15 survey score at preop and post op day 1. Each item was rated on an 11-point scale (0–10), with responses that ranged from 'none of the time' to 'all of the time'. The total score on the QoR-15 ranged from 0 (poorest quality of recovery) to 150 (best quality of recovery) [7]. The questionnaire was administered one day before surgery and on post-operative day 1 by researchers who were unaware of the group assignments.

Results

In this study, 60 adult female patients undergoing modified radical mastectomy under GA were divided into two groups. One group received PECS block and the other received ESPB block after induction. The demographic profiles and haemodynamic parameters were comparable between the two groups. Incidence of adverse effects and complications were negligible in both groups. The difference between VAS score of both the groups was not statistically significant throughout the post-operative period except during the 4 hour post-operative period in which PECS was found to be more effective than ESPB ($p=0.026$). The total number of patients requiring more than one rescue dose was higher in ESPB. The time to first rescue analgesia was longer in PECS than in ESPB group ($p<0.001$).

Table 1: Comparison of baseline clinical variables and intraoperative haemodynamics

Variables	ESPB	PECS	Total	P value
Age (years)	43.27±12.6	45.13±12.27	44.2±12.37	0.563
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.94±2.95	24.21±3.6	24.57±3.29	0.392
Weight (kg)	55.6±7.27	54.03±6.79	54.82±7.02	0.392
Height (cm)	149.77±7.44	149.8±5.93	149.78±6.67	0.985
Duration of surgery (h)	2.54±0.56	2.72±0.56	2.63±0.56	0.210
ASA status				
ASA I	7(23.3%)	10(33.3%)	17(28.3%)	0.451
ASA II	20(66.7%)	20(66.7%)	40(66.7%)	
ASA III	3(10.0%)	0	3(5.0%)	
Intraop vitals				
Heart rate (/min)	80.03±9.97	78.23±8.94	79.13±9.43	0.465
Systolic BP (mmHg)	131.5±14.57	132.2±11.81	131.85±13.15	0.839
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	79.9±8.62	79.53±8.14	79.72±8.32	0.866

As shown in table 1, the distribution between the two groups regarding the age, BMI, height, weight, duration of surgery, ASA grading, intra op heart rate and blood pressure variables were not significant.

Table 2: VAS score - Frequency distribution

Variables	Score (0-10)	ESPB N (%)	PECS N (%)	Total N (%)	Chi-square	p-value	Fisher exact
VAS 2 h	0	5(16.7)	1(3.3)	6(10)			
	1-3	25(83.3)	29(96.7)	54(90)	2.963	0.085	0.195
VAS 4 h	0	7(23.3)	3(10)	10(16.7)			
	1-3	23(76.7)	21(70)	44(73.3)			
	4-6	0(0)	6(20)	6(10)	7.691	0.021	0.026
VAS 6 h	0	15(50)	8(26.7)	23(38.3)			
	1-3	9(30)	9(30)	18(30)			
	4-6	6(20)	13(43.3)	19(31.7)	4.709	0.095	0.099
VAS 8 h	0	15(50)	11(36.7)	26(43.3)			
	1-3	10(33.3)	18(60)	28(46.7)			
	4-6	5(16.7)	1(3.3)	6(10)	5.588	0.062	0.071
VAS 24 h	0	23(76.7)	16(53.3)	39(65)			
	1-3	7(23.3)	14(46.7)	21(35)	3.59	0.58	0.103

Chi-Square/ Fisher Exact test used

As shown in table 2, the VAS score was not significant between the two groups except during the 4 hours post-operative period in which PECS was found to be more effective than ESPB.

Table 3: Number of rescue doses and time to first rescue dose

	No of doses	ESPB N (%)	PECS N (%)	Total n (%)	Chi-square	p-value	Fisher exact
Rescue dose	1	23(76.7)	30(100)	53(88.3)	7.925	0.005	0.011
	2	7(23.3)	0(0)	7(11.7)			
time to first rescue dose in h (median)		6 (4-8)	14(12-16)			<0.001	

Table 4: Complications of blocks

Complications	ESPB n (%)	PECS n (%)	Total n (%)
Nil	30(100)	26(86.7)	56(93.3)
Yes	0(0)	4(13.3)	4(6.7)
Total	30(100)	30(100)	60(100)

P=0.112, Not Significant, Fisher Exact Test

Table 5: Duration Of Hospital Stay (Days) - Frequency distribution

Duration Of Hospital Stay (Days)	ESPB n (%)	PECS n (%)	Total n(%)
1	26(86.7)	24(80)	50(83.3)
2	4(13.3)	6(20)	10(16.7)
Total	30(100)	30(100)	60(100)

P=0.730, Not Significant, Fisher Exact Test

Table 6: Comparison of QoR in two groups of patients studied

Variables	ESPB (Mean±SD)	PECS (Mean±SD)	Total (Mean±SD)	P Value
QoR 15 preop	139.23±4.88	138.67±4.49	138.95±4.66	0.642
QoR postop day 1	133.53±4.02	146.03±3.01	139.78±7.22	<0.001**
Difference	5.70	7.37	-0.83	-
P value	<0.001**	<0.001**	0.386	-

Statistical analysis: Descriptive and inferential statistical analysis was carried out in the present study. Results on continuous measurements were presented on mean ± SD (Min-Max) and results on categorical measurements were presented in number (%).

Significance was assessed at 5% level of significance. Student t test (two tailed, independent) was used to find the significance of study parameters on continuous scale between two groups on metric

parameters. Leven's test for homogeneity of variance was performed to assess the homogeneity of variance. Student t test (two tailed, dependent) was used to find the significance of study parameters on continuous scale within each group. Chi-square/ Fisher Exact test was used to find the significance of study parameters on categorical scale between two or more groups, Non-parametric setting for qualitative data analysis.

Fisher Exact test used when cell samples are very small.

Significant figures

+ Suggestive significance (P value: $0.05 < P < 0.10$)

* Moderately significant (P value: $0.01 < P \leq 0.05$)

** Strongly significant (P value: $P \leq 0.01$)

Statistical software: The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 22.0, and R environment ver.3.2.2 were used for the analysis of the data and Microsoft word and Excel were used to generate graphs, tables etc.

Discussion

In this study, 60 adult female patients undergoing modified radical mastectomy under GA were divided into two groups. One group received PECS block and the other received ESPB block after induction. The demographic profiles and haemodynamic parameters were comparable between the two groups.

Incidence of adverse effects and complications were negligible in both groups. The difference between VAS score of both the groups was not statistically significant throughout the post-operative period except during the 4 hour post-operative period in which PECS was found to be more effective than ESPB ($p=0.026$). The total number of patients requiring more than 1 rescue dose was more in ESPB. The time to first rescue analgesia was longer in PECS group than ESPB group ($p < 0.001$).

The thoracic epidural analgesia (TEA) and thoracic paravertebral block (PVB) have long been considered the gold standard for providing analgesia in breast surgeries but they are associated with decreased thoracic component of ventilation, increased incidence of hypotension and additional supplemental analgesia requirement for axillary clearance.

The PVB provides ipsilateral dermatomal blockade without block of contralateral sympathetic chain. However, PVB does not block medial and lateral pectoral nerves as well as the long thoracic and thoracodorsal nerves⁸. Coveney et al reported that incidence of inadequacy of block after multiple injections was 15% during axillary dissection. Therefore, during breast surgeries involving axillary dissection, there is lack of adequate analgesia by both these time trusted methods [9].

PECS block when compared with control group has been shown to decrease opioid consumption and VAS score in the 24 hour post-operative period. In a study done by Bashandy GM and colleagues on patients receiving pectoral blocks, the opiate consumption was reduced both intra operatively and

for 12 hours postoperatively and pain scores were reduced for 24 hours postoperatively [10]. Disadvantages of PECS include sparing of supraclavicular nerves and intercostobrachial nerve and disruption of the surgical plane [11].

In 2013, Blanco R reported a variation of his original technique by performing his original PECS 1 block and then adding an additional local anaesthetic injection between the serratus anterior and pectoralis minor muscle (PECS2). The analgesia remained till 8 hours. This modification aimed to extend analgesia to the axilla. PECS II block was found to be superior to thoracic paravertebral block in providing postoperative analgesia in patients undergoing modified radical mastectomy without causing any adverse effects [12]. In a study comparing PVB and pectoral nerve block type II, no statistically significant differences were found in the pain intensity after breast cancer surgery. The time to first analgesic request was longer in Pecs group. This the pectoral nerve block type II can provide postoperative analgesia that is comparable to the single-level thoracic paravertebral block [13].

PECS II is unable to block the anterior cutaneous branches of the intercostal nerves, which innervate the surrounding sternum; thus, PECS II may not be able to block the internal mammary region in the surgical site [14].

ESPB was first described by Forrero et al in 2016 targeting the dorsal and ventral rami of spinal nerve roots in the plane between erector spinae and intercostal muscles to anaesthetize the anterior and posterior chest wall, axilla and medial aspect of upper arm. The ESPB decreased the postoperative pain and opioid consumption when used as part of multimodal analgesia and is an effective block for postoperative analgesia in breast cancer surgery [15].

Studies have shown that ESPB is better than both thoracic epidural and general anaesthesia alone [16]. The analgesic effect of ultrasound-guided ESPB is shown to be significant after radical mastectomy. There are few adverse reactions and few effects on immune function and the postoperative recovery of patients is also boosted [17].

In a case reported by Veiga M, ESPB was given in a 40 year old female patient undergoing radical mastectomy. The block was given before induction of anaesthesia. Opioid sparing effect was seen intraoperatively.

During hospitalization, the patient reported no pain and did not resort to rescue analgesia. In other case reports by Ohgoshi Y and colleagues the area of analgesia was broad on POD 1 and 2, and the patients experienced little or no pain at rest. These

findings were similar to the current study where the VAS was ≤ 4 in group ESP for 21.08 ± 4.53 h post operatively.

Ultrasound-guided erector spinae plane block has been used to provide complete surgical anaesthesia in patient with high cardiovascular risk undergoing breast surgery along with sedation. Patient was pain free and remained haemodynamically stable throughout the 2.5-hour procedure.

At the end of the surgery, patient received morphine 2 mg and dipyrone 2 g intravenously, and demanded no analgesic until 24 hours after the procedure [18]. An RCT where procedures in the ESPB and control blocks were performed on the same side with 0.375% ropivacaine or 0.9% saline (0.4mL/kg) showed the superiority of the ESPB over the control group in the quality of recovery in patients undergoing breast surgery. ESPB lessened pain severity and reduced opioid consumption [19]. However, in breast surgery there are very few comparative studies between PECS and ESPB blocks for post-operative pain relief. Two such studies found modified PECS block to be more effective in reducing the postoperative tramadol consumption and pain scores than ESPB after radical mastectomy surgery [20,21]. However, both the studies were single blinded study where the patients were not being blinded.

Several randomised controlled trials were performed in which PECS block was compared to the ESPB. PECS block was found to be superior to ESPB in terms of VAS scores, rescue analgesics and time to first rescue analgesia [21-26]. However it was found to be inferior to the pectoralis nerve block and its efficacy was similar to paravertebral block [27].

In contrast, a few other studies reported that ESPB was found to be superior to PECS block [28,29].

One of the disadvantages of the ESPB block, compared to that of the PECS block is the variable spread of local anaesthetic in the former, as indicated in cadaveric studies. Adhikary et al. verified dye spread between 5 to 10 intercostal spaces, from 2 to 5 to the epidural space, and 2 to 3 to the intercostal foramina. A more recent and more extensive cadaveric study compared two volumes of dye (i.e., 10 and 30 mL).

The superior costotransverse ligament was stained only in 3 of 7 cadavers at the level T3 and one at the T2 level after injecting 30 mL of the dye. On the other hand, the PECS-II block directly blocks most of the nerve supply of the breast, including pectoral, intercostobrachial, long thoracic, 3 - 6 intercostals, and thoracodorsal nerves [30].

A statistically significant difference in static and dynamic VAS ($p=0.879$; $p=0.917$, respectively) was not found in patients receiving ESPB Vs

SPB+PECS. However, ESPB group required higher value of patient-controlled analgesia (PCA) bolus, no statistically significant difference was found in PCA activation pattern between groups ($p=0.109$).

ESPB was a faster technique when compared to SPB+PECS I ($p=0.007$) and no complications or opioid side-effects were recorded in all groups examined and they concluded that ESPB could represent a safe, faster alternative with a single injection than to SPB+PECS I in BCS31.

Limitations of the study: Small sample size.

Conclusions

This study showed that there is no difference between PECS and ESPB for the post-operative analgesia of patients undergoing mastectomy. Both are excellent modalities for post-operative analgesia in breast surgeries.

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